

1 **APPENDIX S1.** List of species molecularly investigated in this study with their corresponding accession numbers,
2 including plastid and rDNA-cistron for newly sequenced samples, which are indicated with an *. For other
3 samples, are provided the rDNA-cistron, NCBI BioSample, SRA RUN and accession numbers, where NCBI
4 BioSamples and genomic data (raw reads) were deposited under BioProject PRJNA607882 and SRA study
5 SRP253072 at the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA). Further information provided includes information on
6 the collector(s) and collection number as well as the year of collection, followed by the herbarium where the
7 vouchers are deposited, and the location of the collection.

8 **Ingroup:** *Gentiana algida* Pallas*, A. Favre, AFUS_19031 (2019), FR, Yankee Boy Basin, Ouray,
9 Colorado (USA), MZ579509, MW248481. *Gentiana algida* Pallas*, A. Favre, AFUS_19025b (2019), FR, Spirit
10 Lake, Uinta Mts., Utah (USA), MZ579508, MW248480. *Gentiana algida* Pallas*, A. & M. Maximov s.n. (1967),
11 M, Chentej-Czikoi Mts., East Siberia (Russia), MW218876, MW248478. *Gentiana algida* Pallas*, T. Neczaeva
12 s.n. (1970), M, Esso, Kamchatka (Russia), MW218875, MW248477. *Gentiana algida* Pallas*, Staudinger M. I
13 5275 (2002), W, Seminskii Pass, Altai (Russia), MW218874, MW248476. *Gentiana atuntsiensis* W.W. Smith*,
14 A. Favre & S. Matuszak 165a (2011), Shickashan, Shangrila, Yunnan (China), KUN, MW405445, MT079994.
15 *Gentiana erectosepala* T.N. Ho, P.C. Fu, 2016192 (2016), Herbarium Luoyang, Linzhi, Tibet (China), MT079975,
16 SAMN14389702, SRR11321291, SRX7925131. *Gentiana frigida* Haenke*, A. Favre, AFAT_19004 (2018), FR,
17 Hämmerkogel, Steiermark (Austria), -, MW405446. *Gentiana handeliana* Harry Smith, Liu & al., 1209080
18 (2012), LZ, Chayu to Jinjiu Town, Xizang (China), MT079978, SAMN14389674, SRR11321321, SRX7925101.
19 *Gentiana nubigena* Edgeworth, A. Favre et al., AFCN18_051 (2018), HNWP, Amnye Machen, Qinghai,
20 MT079980, SAMN14389675, SRR11321320, SRX7925102. *Gentiana purdomii* C. Marquand*, A. Favre et al.,
21 AFCN18_033a (2018), HNWP, Baitang Basin, Yushu, Qinghai (China), -, MW405447. *Gentiana susanneae*
22 Adr.Favre*, A. Favre, AFCN18_201e (2018), KUN, Cuopu Lakes, Sichuan (China), MW218877, MW248482.

23 **Outgroup:** *G. cephalantha* Franchet, A. Favre, AFCN_18243 (2018), KUN, Cangshan, Dali, Yunnan
24 (China), MT079987, SAMN14389697, SRR11321296, SRX7925126.

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